

On-chip microfluidic lasers and laser arrays from colloidal quantum-dot cement

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Abstract:

Colloidal quantum dots (QDs) have emerged as promising gain media owing to their solution-processability and broadband tunable emission. However, the practical deployment of QD lasers in demanding environments, such as microfluidic systems, has been hindered by their susceptibility to surface degradation and difficulties in device integration. Herein, we realize a new class of microfluidic lasers based on a QD-in-matrix architecture, termed QD cement, which achieves superior optical gain through a ligand-mediated polymerization strategy. By virtue of the epitaxy-like heterostructure via coordination bonding design, the QD cement exhibits robust stimulated emission featuring simultaneous triple state transitions, along with a record-high saturation intensity. Notably, the malleability of QD cement enables the construction of microlasers and laser arrays with arbitrary geometries and resonant modes that perform reliably in both aqueous and organic solvents. Leveraging this platform, an optofluidic chip and its proof-of-concept application for in-situ liquid monitoring are demonstrated, achieving a high sensitivity of 293 nm/RIU. This work marks a significant step toward practical QD lasers and opens a new avenue for integrated optofluidics and optoelectronics.

1. Introduction

Optofluidic systems that combine the microfluidics and optics are emerging as the promising platform to enable novel functionalities beyond those achievable through either field alone.^[1] The exploitation of fluid-light interaction at the micro/nanoscale holds great potential for developing high-sensitivity, flexible and reconfigurable lab-on-a-chip systems. However, currently, the development of optofluidic chips is severely hindered by the deficiency of qualified laser sources that can be integrated into microfluidic chips in a cost-effective way and operate under harsh environments, such as being surrounded by water and polar organic solvents.^[2]

Colloidal quantum dots (QDs) have emerged as a highly promising class of gain media, owing to their solution processability, high photoluminescence quantum yields (PLQY), and broadly tunable emission spectra spanning from the deep ultraviolet to the infrared region.^[3-4] Over the past two decades, significant advances have been made in the development of amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) sources and novel laser systems based on QD gain media.^[5-7] With the continuous improvements in synthesis techniques and optical cavity architectures, QD lasers are now being increasingly explored across a variety of multidisciplinary applications.^[8-12] However, until now, the integration of QD lasers into microfluidic platforms remains substantially constrained by their sensitive surface chemistry, which often compromises lasing performance under harsh operational conditions.^[2]

Historically, the susceptibility of QD surfaces to environmental disturbance has also limited their utility in lighting and display technologies.^[2, 13-14] Inspired by the biocomposite structures in nature (e.g., photosynthesis), researchers have successfully addressed this limitation by embedding QDs within passive polymer matrices over the past decade.^[15-16] Through extensive investigation, it has been demonstrated that the long polymer chains can encapsulate QDs effectively, forming the stable QD-polymer composites that have now reached commercial adoption in backlight display units.^[17] However, such QD-in-matrix route has proven inadequate for laser applications, primarily due to the difficulty in fabricating QD-polymer hybrids that exhibit sufficient optical gain.^[18] A central issue is that the direct blending of polymers with QDs at high concentrations tends to induce nanoparticle aggregation and fluorescence quenching, which, in turn, suppresses the stimulated emission and undermines lasing performance.^[19] Additionally, the chemical reaction-based methods for dispersing QDs in matrixes often introduce detrimental nonradiative decay pathways, such as defect states arising from surface damage.^[20] Consequently, although such QD-polymer composites perform adequately in spontaneous emission scenarios, they are unable to surpass nonradiative losses to achieve the net optical gain required for lasing action.

In this work, we realize a new class of microfluidic lasers and laser arrays based on a QD-in-matrix structure (i.e., QD cement) with superior optical gain. Specifically, we design a ligand-mediated-polymerization strategy to achieve the exceptional QD dispersion in polymer through the formation of intramolecular interactions. By virtue

of the epitaxy-like heterostructure via coordination bonding design, the QD cement exhibits highly robust ASE with triple state transitions. The achievement of such simultaneous triple-band ASE highlights the exceptional optical gain of the QD cement.^[21-23] Moreover, the ASE exhibits a record-high saturation intensity, leading to a power conversion efficiency approaching ~10%. Notably, the malleability of the QD cement enables the construction of microlasers and laser arrays with arbitrary geometries that support the whispering-gallery-mode (WGM) or wave-chaotic resonances. These QD microlasers operate stably in harsh environments including water and organic polar solvents. On this basis, we demonstrate an optofluidic chip and its proof-of-concept application for in-situ liquid monitoring, achieving a high refractive sensitivity of 293 nm/RIU. This work represents a remarkable advancement toward practical QD-based laser devices.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Design and Characterizations of QD Cement

To achieve the high-density QDs embedded in a passive matrix with favorable optical gain, a strategy to eliminate QD aggregation and ensuing optical degradation is proposed by taking the ligand molecules as the mediator to graft polymer monomers onto the surface of QDs (Figure 1a). In doing so, the adoption of high-gain QDs as the active material is the prerequisite. Here, the CdZnSe/ZnSeS/ZnS ternary alloy QDs were synthesized following the previous report with slight modifications (see

Experimental Section in Supporting Information for synthesis details).^[7] The current QDs utilize monospecific oleic acid (OA) ligands with unsaturated alkenes to cater for the subsequent ligand-mediated-polymerization reaction. The transmission electron microscope (TEM) image (Figure S1, Supporting Information) shows clear lattice fringes, indicating the high crystallinity of the QDs. The optical gain performance of the ternary QDs is explored by the femtosecond transient absorption (TA) spectroscopy (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information). The optical gain is found to occur in a wide spectral range of 570-650 nm (Figure 1b) (Figure S2, Supporting Information). According to the pump fluence dependent gain spectra, a large gain cross-section (σ_g) of $3.4 \times 10^{-15} \text{ cm}^2$ and long gain lifetime (τ_g) of more than 3 ns are derived (Figure S3, Supporting Information). The long gain lifetime is attributed to the suppressed nonradiative Auger recombination (Figure S2c, Supporting Information), known as the main dissipation pathway of the population inversion, in the ternary alloy QDs. As a result, the critical QD density or minimal QD concentration ($n_{min} \approx 0.16 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) for stimulated emission can be estimated relying on the derived values of σ_g and τ_g (Text S1 of Supporting Information). In reality, due to the additional optical losses, such as the scattering and photoinduced absorption, the QD concentration required to maintain light amplification is typically more than 10 times of n_{min} , which cannot be achieved by the prevailing dispersion methods. These methods fail to construct intramolecular interactions between QDs and matrix, which leads to serious aggregation of QDs and causes light scattering as well as inter-dot energy transfer. To

overcome this issue, a covalent bonding approach is proposed. In the event of an interaction between the surface of the QDs and the polymer, the compatibility between them will be enhanced and the phase separation will be mitigated due to a reduction in interfacial energy.^[24] The implementation of chemical bonds between polymer chains and the surface of QDs could effectively prevent aggregation by enveloping the QDs in a steric hindrance.

The ligand-assisted polymerization process can be briefly categorized by the following steps (Figure 1a). First, the prepared OA-capped QDs, monomer (methylmethacrylate, MMA) and initiator were blended with optimized ratios under argon atmosphere (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information). The key is the adoption of the 2,2'-Azobis(2-methylpropionitrile) (AIBN) with low reactivity as the initiator because the radical initiators are recognized as the culprit for the oxidation of QDs, deteriorating the gain properties.^[25-26] Second, the compound was heated to 70 °C under vigorous stirring to generate the radicals from AIBN initiators. The reason for selecting OA as the ligand is that unsaturated alkenes can interact with free radicals and graft monomers onto the ligand molecule (Figure 1a). The free radicals attack the C=C double bond and the breakage of the double bond creates two radical sites, where one carbon atom is bonded to the initial radical and the other carries an unpaired electron.^[27] The chemical reaction formula is expressed as:

where $R\cdot$ is a free radical. Subsequently, the MMA monomer binds to the remaining

radical sites through its double bond, forming a covalent bond and another new radical.^[16, 27] The generated radical, in turn, initiates a chain propagation reaction:

Third, the solution was kept at 45 °C to maintain the equilibrium of polymerization reaction and standby for the following solidification. Based on the covalent bonding design, the high density of QD dispersion of $1.2 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ or $19.4 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ can be achieved, which is more than 100 times of the derived n_{min} (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information), potentially satisfying the light amplification condition.

To confirm and understand the formation of the QD-polymer nanohybrids (i.e., QD cement), the optical property and chemical structure were investigated systematically. The absorption, PL spectra and PL decay kinetics show negligible difference between the QD cement (red line) and the pristine QDs (yellow line) (Figures S4 and S5, Supporting Information), which indicates the retaining of the optical property during the polymerization. The pristine QDs referred to the as-synthesized QDs capped with OA ligands without any post-treatment. The Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra in Figure 1c indicate the covalent bonding of QD ligands to the polymer in the cement. Specifically, after the polymerization reaction, the C=C double bond in the pristine QDs has transformed into C—C single bonds during the grafting process (Figure 1a). Instead, the emergence of the absorption bands at

$\sim 1734\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1149\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the C=O and C—O—C vibrations indicates that the radical and monomer have bound to the surface in the polymer-graft-ligand chain of the cement. The dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurement (Figure 1d) was performed to characterize the QD dispersion. It is found that the QD cement formed by the ligand-mediated-polymerization maintains a narrow size distribution similar to that of pristine QD solution. The TEM of the QD cement (Figure 1e) also demonstrates comparable sizes to the pristine QDs. In contrast, the samples fabricated by using QDs without ligands of unsaturated alkenes (Control-I) and direct blending of QDs with polymer (Control-II) (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information for fabrication details) exhibit significantly enlarged size distributions in DLS, due to the heterogeneous phase aggregation. Specifically, Control-I follows the same polymerization procedure as the QD cement, while the QDs are capped with stearic acid (SA) instead of OA. Since SA is a saturated acid lacking unsaturated alkenes, it cannot participate in the polymerization, leaving the QDs embedded in the polymer without covalent bridging. Control-II is made by directly mixing of the OA-capped QDs into a pre-dissolved PMMA solution. Consistently, the PL lifetimes (τ_{aver}) of Control-I and Control-II are considerably shorter than that of pristine QDs (Figure S5 and Table S1 of Supporting Information), which arises from the aggregation induced quenching in the QDs. The above characterizations demonstrate the excellent compatibility derived from the ligand-mediated bonding between QDs and the polymer.

2.2. Stimulated Emission from QD Cement

The QD cement inherits excellent malleability from the polymer matrix, enabling them to be scrape-coated into large-scale thin films. Figure 2a present a QD-cement film coated on a 2-inch silicon wafer (the bottom photograph shows the sample under UV light). Moreover, the free-standing films of various shapes (Figure 2b) can be obtained by mechanical peeling and clipping (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information for fabrication details), which is not feasible for the pristine QD film.

To explore the stimulated emission property, the QD-cement film supported on the glass substrate was excited by the stripe pumping configuration (400 nm, 1 kHz, 100 fs) (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information). The broad spontaneous emission spectrum with full-width at half maximum (FWHM) of ~22 nm is observed at ~631 nm under low excitation intensity (Figure 2c). As the excitation intensity increases, a narrow emission peak appears at ~641 nm (FWHM: ~5.2 nm) and another peak at ~606 nm (FWHM: ~6.6 nm) with the further rise of pump intensity, which is attributed to the ASE from the band-edge and the subsequent higher-energy transitions.^[28] Consistently, the emission color of the film changes from red to orange as the second ASE band appears (Figure 2d). Interestingly, upon further increasing the pump fluence, a third ASE peak is observed at ~583 nm and the emission color of the film alters to the yellow. The plot of the integrated emission intensity as a function of pump fluence (Figure 2e) reveals the thresholds of these sequential ASE bands to be as low as $2.3 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, $10.0 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, and $26.1 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$, respectively. We further measured the ASE behavior of the pristine QD film, where only the first two ASE peaks can be

achieved until the film was damaged by the high excitation intensity (Figure S6, Supporting Information). These observations highlight the superior gain performance and exceptional irradiation resistance of the QD cement.

As for the origins of the ASE peaks beyond the band-edge transitions, they may correspond to the sequential state-filling of higher quantized levels ordered as 1P and 1D. However, the effects of imperfect spherical symmetry, valence band mixing and electron-hole exchange can enable ASE from the forbidden cross-transitions (e.g., $1P_e-1S_h$ and $1S_e-1P_h$).^[29-32] Moreover, the higher-energy ASE peaks could be possibly stem from the shell transitions.^[21] Currently, the accurate assignment of the ASE peaks is challenging.

Importantly, the ASE intensity keeps increasing as the pump fluence exceeds ~360 times of the threshold value (Figure 2f), revealing a record-high saturation intensity for QDs.^[33] As a result of the nonlinear process, a high power conversion efficiency has been realized. Figure 2f displays the output intensity and conversion efficiency versus the pump intensity. When the pump intensity is below 12.5 W cm^{-2} , the absolute conversion efficiency of the film remains invariable at 9.2%-9.6%. As the pump intensity increases, the conversion efficiency exhibits a slight drop, remaining at 8.2% at pump intensity of 18.2 W cm^{-2} .

To quantify the modal gain coefficient of the QD cement, the variable stripe length (VSL) measurements was conducted. The PL spectra are monitored under a fixed

excitation intensity of $\sim 96.0 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ for different stripe lengths (Figure S7a, Supporting Information). As the excitation length increases, the build-up of the three sequential ASE bands is observed. The integrated ASE intensities from these optical transitions are plotted as a function of stripe length (Figure S7b, Supporting Information), demonstrating high net gain coefficients of ~ 95.2 , ~ 291.6 , and $\sim 377.0 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the first, second, and third ASE bands, respectively.

In addition to the exceptional irradiation resistance, the ASE behavior under harsh conditions (e.g., liquid environments) from the QD cement was tested. By virtue of the epitaxy-like capsulation of the QDs by the polymer matrix via the covalent bonding, the multi-band ASE is found to readily occur in either ethanol or water (Figure S8, Supporting Information). In contrast, the pristine QD film dissociated immediately upon exposure to ethanol and lost its luminescence (Figure S9, Supporting Information). In our QD cement, the dense polymer matrix acts as a robust physical barrier against oxygen and moisture. The covalent anchoring of the polymer chains onto the QD surface via the ligand-mediated polymerization preserves the surface passivation. This architecture effectively prevents ligand desorption and circumvents the typical photo-oxidation pathways, thereby preserving the structural integrity and optical gain over extended periods, which is highly beneficial for laser aspirations.

2.3. Microlasers and Laser Array with Customizable Geometry

By virtue of the malleability and flexibility, the QD cement allows for the fabrication of QD microlasers and laser arrays by both the bottom-up and top-down routes. Figure 3a displays the fabrication of microfiber lasers by the representative bottom-up approach. Specifically, a droplet of QD-cement solution was placed on a substrate and a metal needle was merged into the droplet. Then, the needle was moved slowly in a certain direction to draw up a free-standing microfiber from the droplet. The SEM image of the microfiber shows that the surface is rather smooth (Figure 3a).^[34] Importantly, the QD microfiber exhibits favorable lasing performance in liquid environments as revealed in Figure 3b. The corresponding PL spectra in ethanol show the appearance of sharp and equidistant peaks with the increase of pump fluence, manifesting the development of lasing action. The plot of the integrated PL intensity as a function of pump fluence discloses a low threshold of $\sim 14.3 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ (Figure S10, Supporting Information). By fitting the lasing peaks according to the WGM theory,^[35] the lasing spikes can be well assigned by mode numbers from 1324 to 1335 (Figure 3c), indicating the WGM mechanism for the microfiber laser. The Q-factor is derived to be as high as ~ 8053 (inset of Figure 3b) by the formula: $Q = \lambda/\delta\lambda$, where λ and $\delta\lambda$ are the center wavelength and the FWHM of the lasing peak, respectively. To further confirm the lasing action, we investigated the transient dynamics and polarization characteristics of the QD-cement fiber.^[36] It is found that the PL lifetime (Figure S11, Supporting Information) shortens by three orders of magnitude at pump fluence of $\sim 21.0 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ compared to that of spontaneous emission at low pump fluence in Table

S1, providing a kinetic hallmark for the occurrence of lasing action. Simultaneously, the emission becomes linearly polarized, following a $\sin^2(\theta)$ dependence (Figure S12, Supporting Information). In contrast, the emission does not show any signs of polarization below the lasing threshold. These distinct features, combined with the nonlinear threshold behavior, validate the lasing action from the QD cements.

After that, the top-down method by the subtractive direct laser writing (DLW) technique was employed to tentatively fabricate the laser arrays (Figure 4a) from the QD cement. Such DLW can construct the active relieve patterns on the QD-cement film by pre-programming in the code (Figure 4b). Figures 4c-4e display the QD-cement patterns with different morphologies made by DLW after fine-tuning the parameters (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information for fabrication details). These micro-patterns can support distinct optical resonance modes to develop on-demand laser characteristics. Figures 4f-4h show the corresponding pump fluence dependent PL spectra from the QD-cement patterns. The appearance of evenly spaced peaks with narrow linewidth indicates the development of lasing action, which is further confirmed by the nonlinear increase of the PL intensity as a function of pump fluence (Figure S13, Supporting Information). The lasing resonance can be ascertained by the numerical simulations, where the microdisk demonstrates a typical WGM resonance (inset of Figure 4f). The electric-field distribution of the square pattern (inset of Figure 4d) shows a periodic four-bounced trajectory, corresponding to the quasi-WGM resonance^[37]. For the stadium-shaped pattern (inset of Figure 4h), the field distribution

appears to be disordered compared to that of WGM, while certain wavefunctions are localized on the unstable periodic orbits (UPOs) with a high density.^[38-39] These long-lived modes are consistent with the characteristics of scar modes in wave chaos scenario.^[38-39] Similar lasing features are also verified in the top-down fabricated microcavities. For instance, the circular microcavities exhibit identical polarized emission above the threshold (Figure S14).

2.4. On-Chip Microfluidic Laser and Optofluidic Sensor

Leveraging the laser operation in liquid environments, an optofluidic chip was designed and fabricated. The schematic illustration of the optofluidic chip and the corresponding photograph of the device are presented in Figure 5a (see Experimental Section in Supporting Information for fabrication details). In the device, the QD microfiber was fixed inside the microchannel near the outlet, where water as the environment medium flowed in through the Inlet 1 and tetrahydrofuran (THF) flowed in through the Inlet 2 to tune the refractive index of the medium. To understand the lasing resonance under the liquid medium, the electric-field distribution in the transverse cross-section of the microfiber is simulated (inset of Figure 5b). The plot of the typical nodes representing the standing waves indicates that light is well confined within the fiber in the liquid environment, while the evanescent wave-mediated optical leakage can be disclosed near the fiber surface, which serves to detect the tiny changes in the surrounding. The

corresponding normalized radial intensity distribution of the cavity resonance is presented in Figure 5b.

Initially, only water was flowed into the microchannel and the WGM lasing spectrum was monitored in-situ from the top view (bottom line of Figure 5c). Subsequently, a certain amount of THF was injected from Inlet 2. The resonance peaks were observed to undergo obvious redshift. The plot of the shift of peak ($\Delta\lambda$) as a function of the refractive index variation (Δn) displays a linear relationship (Figure 5d).^[40] The fitting of the data reveals a high sensitivity of 293 nm/RIU, which is attributed to the high Q-factor of the WGM lasing and the sensitivity of the evanescent field interaction. Thanks to the robustness of the QD laser, the results are reproducible over tens of cycles and the device remains intact after one year.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we realize the robust microfluidic lasers and laser arrays by a QD-in-matrix architecture. The QD cement allows the fabrication of lasers and laser arrays with customizable geometry in cost-effective methods. Owing to the robust operation in harsh environment, the QD cement was utilized to construct the on-chip microfluidic laser, which exhibits high sensitivity on the refractive change. We can envisage that the microfluidic laser could serve as the versatile coherent light sources and be exploited for detecting biomolecules and toxic chemicals, which can provide new possibilities for integrated optofluidic and optoelectronics.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

Keywords

Quantum dots, microlaser, laser array, optofluidic chip, microfluidic laser

Figure 1. Design and characterizations of QD cement. a) Step-by-step progression of ligand-assisted polymerization to form QD cement. b) Nonlinear absorption spectra of the ternary QDs obtained by adding the TA spectra ($\Delta\alpha$) at different pump fluences to the ground-state absorption (α_0). c) FTIR spectra of pristine QD film and QD-cement film. d) DLS measurements of solutions of pristine QDs, QD cement and the control samples. e) TEM image of the QD cement (scale bar: 20 nm).

Figure 2. ASE from the QD-cement film. a) Photographs of a QD-cement film on a monocrystalline silicon wafer. Scale bar: 1 inch. b) Photographs of the free-standing QD-cement films with different shapes. Scale bar: 2 cm. c) PL spectra of QD-cement film under varied pump fluences. d) Photographs of the QD-cement film under different excitation intensities. e) Integrated emission intensities of the first, second and third ASE bands (circles, diamonds and stars, respectively) as a function of pump fluence. f) Plot of output intensity and absolute power conversion efficiency as a function of pump intensity.

Figure 3. Bottom-up fabrication of QD microfiber laser. a) Schematic of the fabrication of QD-cement fiber by direct drawing from a QD-cement droplet. Inset: SEM images of a QD-cement fiber (left scale bar: 100 μm ; right scale bar: 50 μm). b) PL spectra of a QD-cement fiber immersed in ethanol under varied pump fluences. Insets show a microscope photograph (left, scale bar: 200 μm) and a magnification of individual lasing peak (right), respectively. c) Mode analysis of the lasing spectrum with the azimuthal mode numbers from 1324 to 1335.

Figure 4. Top-down fabrication of QD laser arrays. a) Schematic of subtractive DLW for ablation writing. b) Schematic of an individual micro-pattern as an optical cavity. Microscopic images and corresponding electric-field distributions of c) circular, d) square, and e) stadium-shaped structures (scale bar: 200 μm). Lasing spectra of f) circular, g) square, and h) stadium cavities. The corresponding threshold behaviors are presented in Figure S13 in Supporting Information.

Figure 5. Optofluidic chip and in-situ liquid sensing. a) Schematic of optofluidic chip and the photographs of the device. b) Normalized intensity distribution of the transverse cross-section of the microfiber laser, a represents the distance relative to radius R . Inset: The distribution of electric-field intensity in the transverse cross-section. c) Lasing spectra from the QD microfiber under varied THF concentration. d) Shift of a lasing peak ($\Delta\lambda$) as a function of the refractive index variation (Δn) of THF solution compared with water. The experimental data (dots) are fitted by a linear line.

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